

Reinforced room temperature spin filtering in chiral paramagnetic metallopeptides

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ABSTRACT: Chirality-induced spin selectivity (CISS), whereby helical molecules polarize the spin of electrical current, is an intriguing effect with potential applications in nanospintronics. In this nascent field, the study of the CISS effect using paramagnetic chiral molecules, which could introduce another degree of freedom in controlling the spin transport, remains so far unexplored. To address this challenge, herein, we propose the use of self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) of helical lanthanide-binding peptides. In order to elucidate the effect of the paramagnetic nuclei, monolayers of the peptide coordinating paramagnetic or diamagnetic ions are prepared. By means of spin-dependent electrochemistry, CISS effect is demonstrated by cyclic voltammetry and electrochemical impedance measurements for both samples. Additionally, an implementation of the standard liquid-metal drop electron transport setup has been carried out, demonstrating their suitability for solid-state devices. Remarkably, the inclusion of a paramagnetic center in the peptide increases the spin polarization as independently proved by different techniques. These findings permit the inclusion of magnetic biomolecules in the CISS field, paving the way to their implementation in a new generation of (bio)spintronic nanodevices.

The discovery of the giant and tunnel magnetoresistance (GMR and TMR) gave rise to the field of spintronics:^{1,2} the use of the electronic spin in addition to the electronic charge to transport and process information. Typically, inorganic materials had been used as active electronic elements of such devices. However, the study of spin-related phenomena in molecular systems have garnered considerable attention in the last years, allowing the extension from inorganic into molecular spintronics. Since then, researchers have started to profit from the rich diversity of molecules that chemistry and nature can provide, to combine and improve the functional components of a spintronic device. The molecular spintronics field is young but prolific, and recent experimental advances³⁻⁵ have been supported by the theoretical evaluation of various molecular families⁶.

⁷ and biomolecules such as peptides and DNA strands.⁸

In this scenario, chiral molecules play a singular role since Naaman and others showed a net spin polarization of the current in the electronic transport along diamagnetic chiral molecules. This phenomenon, dubbed as Chirality Induced Spin Selectivity (CISS)⁹, proves that chiral molecules can behave as molecular-based spin filters. During the last years, CISS origin has been deeply studied by theoretical calculations, occasionally combined with experiments.¹⁰⁻²⁰ Moreover, it has been recently proposed to be of relevance in different issues like the role of spin in electron transfer through bio-systems,²¹ the building of spintronic logic devices based on organic ferromagnets at room temperature²² or the fabrication of a spintronic magnetic memory which, including a ferromagnetic platelet, presents memristor-like behavior.²³ Since its discovery, the CISS effect has been intensely explored both in single molecules²⁴ and in thin layers, ranging from Langmuir-Blodgett films of L- or D- stearoyl lysine²⁵ to self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) of polyalanine,²⁶ double-strand DNA,²⁷ bacteriorhodopsin^{28,29} and helicene molecules.³⁰ Parallely, the possibility of inducing room temperature spin-dependent transport has also been probed through non-chiral molecules with a single paramagnetic ion.³¹ Remarkably, the specific electronic configuration of the metallic centers turned out to be decisive for the spin-polarized current.³² However, so far, the combination of chirality and paramagnetism in molecular spin filters has remained elusive.

In this context, we identified the family of helical metallopeptides known as Lanthanide Binding Tags (LBTs) as a promising system for CISS-based biospintronics. LBTs were originally designed by Imperiali *et al.* to achieve a high affinity for lanthanoid ions.³³⁻³⁶ Interestingly, they autonomously and robustly fold into a partially helical structure (3₁₀ helix), where one of the atoms in the coordination sphere directly coordinates the lanthanoid ion (Ln³⁺) through a carbonyl group belonging to a peptide bond.³⁷ Since the current in peptides has been known to flow through the

Fig. 1 Structure of the MLBTC metallopeptide used for spin filtering studies. **a** Side view of MLBTC in ribbon representation (based on a structure with PDB ID: 1TJB); arrow shows the right-handed helicity. The aminoacids coordinating the metal ion are tagged (Asp1, Asn3, Asp5, Trp7, Glu12, Glu14), including those coordinating through different lateral residues and the Trp containing the coordinating carbonyl oxygen. **b** and **c** Schemes of spin-dependent transport setups used in this work emphasizing the magnetization of the Ni layer under an external magnetic field (350 mT) and its influence on the empty and occupied density of states, as well as the expected CISS effect of the right-handed helical MLBTC SAM. **b** Three-electrode electrochemical cell consisting of MLBTC SAM on (Ni/Au) as working electrode (WE), Ag/AgCl reference electrode (RE) and Pt wire as a counter electrode (CE) in a buffered 5 mM $K_4Fe(CN)_6/K_3Fe(CN)_6$ solution as an external redox probe. **c** Home-made liquid-metal EGaIn transport system.

backbone chain,³⁸ some reciprocal influence between the spin polarization of the current along the helical backbone and the spin orientation of the lanthanoid ion could be expected.

Recently, our group has shown that they can be used as spin tags to open a fruitful playground in the field of molecular spin qubits,³⁹ thanks to the ease of preparing new structures with optimized properties by means of standard techniques of molecular biology. Furthermore, LBTs have also been used to obtain insight into the real-time interaction between the dynamics of spin energy levels and internal molecular motions.⁴⁰ Here, we prove the spin polarization effect in LBT SAMs and demonstrate a non-innocent role of the paramagnetic center. By means of spin dependent electrochemistry,⁴¹ spin dependent local transport in solid state devices using liquid-metal drop contacts, and DFT transport calculations, we show the potential of LBT SAMs for spin filtering beyond the CISS effect.

Results and discussion

Surface assembling of metalloLBTC units

For our experiments, we selected a LBT sequence³⁷ modified with an additional cysteine (LBTC, see Fig. 1a) at the C-terminal position. This ensure a strong metal-S interaction between the biomolecule and a metallic surface like Au or Ni, which is an essential requirement for the performance of spin-dependent transport measurements. We prepared the peptide and metallopeptide-based SAMs by overnight immersion

in aqueous buffered LBTC or LBTC with Tb^{3+} (TbLBTC) solutions and a reducing agent (tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine) to avoid thiol oxidation during the grafting process (see SI section S1). The presence of the molecules on the surface was confirmed through the identification of the LBTC fragments, extracted by time-of-flight mass spectrometry (see SI section S3). At the same time, the anchoring and the chemical composition were proved by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, which shows the presence of terbium and sulfur (see SI section S4). Moreover, quartz crystal microbalance measurements suggested an almost complete molecular coverage (see SI section S6) and atomic force microscopy (see SI section S2) gave us insight into their homogeneous topography and roughness. The persistence of the lanthanide ion bound to the LBTC peptide on the surface was experimentally supported by its luminescence emission (see SI section S1, Fig. S1.2). The stability, tilt angle and orientation of the three-dimensional folding are consistent with our estimation of the SAM thickness (see SI section S7). More importantly, previous works have demonstrated by using the SHAPE program³⁹ and Q values,⁴² the high similarity between different reported crystal structures as well as solution structures of several LnLBT metallopeptides.⁴² It is well established now that the folding of LBT peptides is very robust and essentially indistinguishable in solution or in solid state. This means no relevant change in helicity or metal coordination is expected in our SAMs regardless of the coordination atom. Instead, a narrow distribution of shapes is expected for the peptides at room temperature due to thermal effects.⁴⁰

Fig. 2 Magnetic field-dependent electrochemistry. **a-c** Spin-dependent cyclic voltammograms of an $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ solution using different working electrodes: a TbLBTC SAM on Ni/Au (a); a YLBTC SAM on Ni/Au (b), and a bare Ni/Au (c). Voltammograms were recorded at 20 mV/s under an external magnetic field pointing “up” (solid red line) or “down” (solid blue line); 4 cycles were averaged. **d-f** Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) of an $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ solution using a TbLBTC SAM on Ni/Au (d) a YLBTC SAM on Ni/Au (e) and a bare Ni/Au (f) as working electrodes respectively. An external magnetic field pointing “up” (red circles) or “down” (blue squares) was applied during the measurements. Zooms of the corresponding plots in the high frequency region (from 10^5 to 10^3 Hz) are shown in the insets. Solid lines in d-f plots are the EIS fits obtained by using the equivalent circuit described in **g**.

Spin-dependent electrochemistry

Once the possibility of assembling metalloLBTC (MLBTC) complexes onto metallic surfaces was demonstrated, their spin filtering properties were investigated by spin-dependent electrochemical measurements. For these experiments, MLBTC functionalized ferromagnetic Ni/Au substrates (200 nm Ni protected with 5 nm Au overlayer), were used as working electrodes (WE), and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6/\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ as a redox-active external probe, due to the non-electroactive nature of the SAMs. As expected, scan rate dependence measurements confirmed that a diffusion process limits this redox reaction⁴³ (see SI section S8).

Next, by placing a permanent magnet ($H = 350$ mT) underneath the WE, spin-dependent cyclic voltammetry measurements were carried out. This is

a well-established technique to measure the spin-selective electron conduction (Fig. 1b)⁴¹ and can be applied to probe Ni/Au/MLBTC electrodes spin filtering potential (Fig. 2) in the $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6/\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ redox solution.

The results showed that the current density in the case of the bare Ni/Au WE was quasi-independent of the orientation of the magnet placed underneath, with the differences for each magnetic field direction being comparable with those observed for two consecutive voltammetry scans (Fig. 2c). When the MLBTC-modified WE was used, the current density decreased dramatically. This is expected due to the presence of the insulating SAM in the WE. Additionally, in contrast with the unmodified WE, a clear dependency of the current density with the magnetic field was recorded in the MLBTC-WE. Higher values of current density were displayed with the magnetic field pointing “down” -i.e. when the north pole of the

external magnet points towards the substrate-compared to the experiments with the magnetic field pointing "up". Furthermore, a shift in the oxidation and reduction potentials of the Ni/Au/MLBTC systems by changing the orientation of the magnet was observed (Fig. 2a-b). These dependencies of the current densities and redox potentials with the magnetic field are a product of the spin selectivity exhibited by the SAM.

We define the spin polarization (*SP*) as:

$$SP = \frac{J_{up} - J_{down}}{J_{up} + J_{down}} \times 100$$

where J_{up} , and J_{down} stand for current density ($J_i = I_i/Area$) at specific potential when the magnetic south pole of the substrate is pointing towards or away from the monolayer, respectively. For the Ni/ Au/ TblBTC, $SP = -3.3 (\pm 0.2)\%$ measured at +460 mV, and $-1.9 (\pm 0.2)\%$ at -70 mV (vs. Ag/AgCl) with a scan rate of 20 $mV \cdot s^{-1}$ were obtained. Moreover, the anodic and cathodic peak shifts -28 mV and -20 mV, respectively.

The spin-dependent voltammograms and thereby deduced spin-polarization results are consistent with the effect of the right-handed helicity of the molecule in our experimental setup (Fig 1b) as reported previously.⁴⁴ The external Nd magnet below the TblBTC modified WE govern the orientation of the magnetization of spins in the Ni layer, which in turn determines the energy of the spin-up vs. the spin-down bands in the Au layer near the Fermi level (E_F). When the external magnetic field is pointing "down", the Ni layer will be polarized accordingly. Independently of the magnet direction, right-handed helices spin-polarize moving electrons in the direction antiparallel to the direction of their movement. For our experiments, this implies that, with the magnet pointing "down", the system displays a better conductance, whether this means "down" electrons flowing upwards (extracted from the Ni valence band) or "up" electrons flowing downwards (injected into the Ni conduction band).

Interestingly, when the diamagnetic Y^{3+} center replaces the paramagnetic Tb^{3+} , *SP* effect was slightly decreased, displaying *SP* of $-0.6 (\pm 0.2)\%$ measured at $E_{pc} = +515$ mV, and $-1.9 (\pm 0.2)\%$ at $E_{pa} = -140$ mV (vs. Ag/AgCl). Additionally, the anodic and cathodic shift of the oxidation and reduction potential also decreases respect its paramagnetic counterpart, -21 and -11 mV respectively (Fig 2a-b).

This experimental observation suggested an increase in the filtering of the SAM, product of the magnetic behavior of the metallic center. Nevertheless, due to the high voltages applied to the sample during the measurements, modification in the SAM packing can occur, complicating the quantitative comparison of the *SP* between samples.

Therefore, to confirm the reliability of this experimental observation, Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were carried out. To the best of our knowledge, this work represents the first time that the EIS technique has been employed for the study of the CISS effect. The EIS is a powerful technique to investigate further and characterize electrochemical charge-transfer processes. While typical direct current voltammetry requires direct current and the application of high voltage, up to 0.5 V, potentially affecting the packing of the SAM, lower voltages are applied in EIS (voltage amplitude of 0.01V). Therefore, the structural rearrangements produced by the flow of current are minimized.

For the evaluation of electron-transfer properties under the influence of an external magnetic field pointing either "up" or "down", an AC potential of 10 mV going from 10^5 to 10^0 Hz was applied at the Open Circuit Potential. Fig. 2d and e display the Nyquist plot of the response of the corresponding electrochemical systems. The equivalent circuit used to fit the data is shown in Fig. 2g. Constant phase element (CPE), which is a non-ideal capacitance, is introduced to provide a good match with the experimental data because of the possible surface roughness, physical non-uniformity, and/or the non-uniform distribution of the electroactive sites. The equivalent circuit is composed of a resistance coming from the ionic transport through the solution (R_s) connected in series with a first parallel branch (R_{int} and C_{int}) corresponding to the electron that has to move through the current collectors and the different layers of the WE. These three elements appear in the high-frequency region. On the other hand, the low-frequency region is associated with a second parallel branch corresponding to the charge transfer and its interfacial double layer capacitance (R_{CT} and CPE_{dl}) taking place between the SAM-modified WE and the electrolyte. As it can be noticed, at high frequencies, the first semicircle remain unaltered after modifying the magnetic field sense. Contrary to that, the second semicircle, that involve the redox process of $K_4Fe(CN)_6/K_3Fe(CN)_6$, is clearly affected. With the external magnet pointing "down", this semicircle is reduced. In this direction, the more depressed the semicircle in the Nyquist plot, the lower the charge transfer resistance. Thus, a reduction of the resistance is observed by changing an external magnet from "up" to "down". A similar trend was observed when the working electrode was magnetized with spin "down" first followed by spin "up" (see Fig. S8.3).

Remarkably, it was found a *SP* of $-3.6 (\pm 0.2) \%$ for the TblBTC and $-2.4 (\pm 0.2) \%$ for the YlBTC. This strongly points out to the active role of the metallic center in the spin selectivity. A blank measurement (*i.e.* without peptide and metal ion) was also carried

Fig. 3 Magnetic field-dependent liquid-metal transport experiments measured for **a** C18S **b** Ala8 **c** YLBTC **d** TbLBTC. Current density histograms measured at ± 0.15 V (top) and averaged current density vs. voltage curves (middle) measured under an external magnetic field pointing “up” (red) or “down” (blue). *SP* polarization as a function of the bias voltage calculated from the measured averaged current density (bottom). In all cases, the sign criterion is such that negative *SP* means the device is more conductive with the magnetic field pointing down.

out to ascertain the spin polarization effect. In Fig. 2f the absence of peptide facilitates the charge transfer leading to a significant decrease of R_{CT} (around 4 orders of magnitude). Importantly, both semicircles exhibit almost no variation after altering the magnetic field position. Indeed, these small differences are reliably related to experimental error.

Liquid metal EGaIn transport measurements

Once cyclic voltammograms and impedance measurements demonstrated the spin selectivity, we advance towards a solid-state characterization, that will be closer to a practical device. To do so, we investigated magnetic field dependent charge-transport through MLBTC with liquid-metal contacts using the Gallium Indium Eutectic alloy (EGaIn) as liquid-metal contacts (Fig. 1c). Liquid-metal drop local transport in solid-state devices has been widely used in electronic current transport measurements in organic layers⁴⁵, and here we have extended it to CISS measurements by including an additional static magnetic field.

Before performing any spin-dependent measurement, to gain local information on the electron transport through MLBTC SAMs, we performed charge-transport studies using Au/TbBTC/Ga₂O₃/EGaIn liquid contact junctions. For statistics, a total of 30 different junctions with areas ranging from ~ 3200 to $\sim 12000 \mu\text{m}^2$ were measured with about 16 *I-V* scans (between -0.5 and 0.5 V) collected on each one. Compared to the pristine samples (without SAM), in the case of the TbBTC SAM the vast majority of the junctions ($>90\%$) showed lower current densities with $\log(|J/A \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}|) = \sim -1$, roughly three orders of magnitude lower than the pristine sample that displayed $\log(|J/A \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}|) = \sim 2$, both measured at 0.15 V (Fig. S9.1a).

To estimate the energy offset (ϵ_0) between Fermi energy (E_F) of electrical contact and the energy of the nearest conduction orbital of the metalloprotein of study, $\epsilon_0 = |E - E_F|$, we used a single-level model with Lorentzian transmission (Newns–Anderson model)⁴⁶. Fitting of the *I-V* curves up to ± 500 mV yielded $\epsilon_0 = 0.68 \pm 0.18$ eV on average (a representative *I-V* curve and its fit are shown in Fig. S9.1b). This value is close to that measured using transition voltage spectroscopy (TVS). In order to measure the transition voltage (V_t), we collected additional *I-V* scans up to ± 1 V. A Fowler-Nordheim plot reveals an average value $V_t = 0.82 \pm 0.10$ V and $\epsilon_0 = 0.71$ eV (SI Fig. S9.1c). This information combined with the change in the absolute value of the electrode work function (Φ), due to the adsorbed TbLBTC SAM, $\Phi_{\text{SAM}} = 4.62$ eV (measured through a combination of Kelvin probe and ambient pressure photoemission spectroscopy, see SI section S10), led to the energy level alignment scheme of Au/TbLBTC//Ga₂O₃/EGaIn junction proposed in Fig. S9.2.

In order to exploit the spin filtering effect in a solid-state device, we extended the experimental setup with the addition of a permanent magnet ($H = 350$ mT) in close proximity to the sample (with an additional ferromagnetic Ni layer). To validate our experimental setup, we prepared and measured two analogous devices based on SAMs of different molecules, including chiral and achiral SAMs. The achiral molecule was octadecanethiol (C18SH) and the chiral reference was the right-handed HS-CH₂-CH₂-NHCO(Ala-AiB)₈-NH₂ (Ala8),⁴⁷ where Ala = Alanine and AiB = 2-aminoisobutyric acid. We measured from 6 to 22 consecutive *I-V* curves for a given drop size. From these data, we calculated the current density *J* vs. applied voltage *V*. Once up to 6 non short-circuited *I-V* curves were

collected, the sample was displaced laterally with an XYZ-stage, where a new EGaIn drop was produced, and the characterization was repeated all over again. To improve the significance level, we repeated this process at least 10 times on randomly selected different parts of the film surface and collected at least 60 I - V curves for each sample. From these data, we calculated the current density J vs. applied voltage V for magnet “up” and “down” orientations. Fig. 3 shows current density histograms measured at ± 0.2 V for opposing directions of the external magnet.

In the case of the achiral C18SH SAMs, no difference in the current density histograms for two different magnetic field directions of the external magnet was observed (Fig. 3a), in contrast to Ala8 case (Fig. 3b). Therefore, negative SP was only observed for helical molecules ($SP \approx 2 \pm 2\%$ for C18S, $SP \approx -40 \pm 15\%$ for Ala8).

Once the feasibility of the set up was proved, spin-dependent solid-state charge-transport measurements of the TblBTC and YLBTC SAMs were carried out. It must be noticed that, similarly to Ala8 SAMs, MLBTC SAMs chirality is expected to be right-handed, and thus to provide a negative SP .⁴⁴ As it was already demonstrated by the electrochemistry measurements (Fig. 2), the SP differs according to the metallic center present in the peptide containing SAMs. In both cases, negative SP s are recorded. However, the filtering effect on the spin selectivity displayed by the paramagnetic SAM is considerably larger than the one displayed by its diamagnetic analogue ($SP \approx -50 \pm 20\%$ for YLBTC and $SP \approx -70 \pm 10\%$ for TblBTC, Fig. 3). Noticeably, SP measured employing liquid metal contacts are of the same sign but nearly one order of magnitude larger compared with those obtained by electrochemical measurements. We attribute this fact to the more local nature of this technique. The unavoidable presence of pin-holes in the SAM should result in a supply of unpolarized electrons that will contribute to the total measured current, and in turn, this will account for a reduction of the measured SP . In this case contribution of spin-dependency to the observed current is negligible. In electrochemical measurements, due to the larger contact surface, which is about 1500 times the contact area generated with EGaIn drops, this effect is maximized.⁴⁸ While, in the case of electrochemical measurements, the presence of TblBTC SAMs results in a moderate decrease of J compared to the pristine substrate, a three order of magnitude decrease is measured in the case of liquid metals.

Theoretical support to predict the influences of the paramagnetic Ln^{3+} on transport properties.

We now aim at estimating the upper limit of the spin filtering effect created by a lanthanide ion (which is here assumed to be fully polarized) on the current, initially neglecting the effect of the CISS. As a first

step, we carried out structural relaxation calculations using the software SIESTA.⁴⁹ After this step, we employed a non-equilibrium Green function approach, using the code SMEAGOL⁵⁰ to obtain the transport properties of the junction (see SI section S11 for details). We used the calculated Density of States (DOS) to obtain the final spin-dependent transmission spectra normalized to the Fermi energy (E_F), as shown in Fig. 4b. We found a small transmission peak at $E - E_F = -0.3$ eV, which, when integrating between -0.5 eV and $+0.5$ eV, results in a spin filtering of about $SP = -70\%$ assuming a complete polarization of the lanthanide ion, *i.e.* at very high magnetic fields or very low temperatures. The position of the peak is at a smaller voltage compared with the experimentally estimated $|E - E_F| = 0.7$ eV but still comparable with the experimentally proposed energy level alignment scheme (Fig. S9.2).

We then studied the Local Density of States at $E - E_F = -0.3$ eV, and confirmed that the nearest transmission orbital is indeed extended all over the peptide backbone (see Fig. S11.2). It means that this path strongly overlaps with the f magnetic orbitals of the lanthanide ion. In other words, the magnetic orbitals of the lanthanoid participate in the singly occupied molecular orbital (SOMO) transmission peak that appears at moderate voltages. Due to this uncommon feature, the effective exchange coupling is expected to be anomalously large. In fact, it is deemed to be within the typical range for lanthanide ions directly coordinated to organic radicals, that corresponds to a magnetic exchange coupling $J_{ex} = 1-25\text{cm}^{-1}$.⁵¹⁻⁵⁴ In this particular case, we estimated this level splitting with additional DFT calculations, (see SI section S12) obtaining differences between the ferro- and antiferromagnetic states of the order of $\sim 5\text{cm}^{-1}$.

This calculated upper limit of $SP = -70\%$ to the effect of the Tb is an obvious overestimation in this case, considering it would require the Tb^{3+} ion to be fully polarized. In the opposite extreme, the effect derived from a magnetic polarization in thermal equilibrium is estimated to have a negligible effect ($SP' = -0.1\%$, see details in SI section S12). However, this is expected to be an underestimation. We need to recall that, as long as current is circulating, the system is out of equilibrium. In particular, since this current is spin polarized by the CISS effect, the magnetization of the Tb^{3+} ion will also be out of equilibrium. Moreover, due to the chiral environment, the ion could be at least partially spin polarized even without current passing through it. The actual result will thus lie between the two extreme scenarios, coinciding with the experimental observation of a modest, but evident, effect of the lanthanoid ion reinforcing the spin polarization, which matches our experimental observation.

Conclusions

Spin filtering enhancement induced by the encapsulated paramagnetic ion has been demonstrated

in lanthanide binding peptides. The active role of the paramagnetic ion has been unambiguously confirmed by three independent experimental approaches: cyclic voltammetry, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and local transport in solid state devices using liquid-metal drop contacts. In the best conditions, a spin polarization $SP = -70 \pm 10 \%$ was achieved with the contribution of complexed Tb^{3+} ions.

The interaction between paramagnetism and chirality in the same molecule is intriguing, since they are two fundamentally different mechanisms for spin filtering. Spin-dependent transport calculations have been performed to shed some light on the experimentally observed behavior, and confirmed an interaction between the magnetic polarizations of the current and the lanthanide ion.

Fig. 4 Calculated spin filtering effect due to the paramagnetic lanthanide **a** Structure of the total region (including the electrodes) that has been used as a model for the calculation. Note that the system has periodic boundary conditions in x - y metal plane while no boundary is considered in the transport z direction where the bulk Au electronic structure is simulated by the non equilibrium Green's function method (depicted as transparent gold layers in the scheme). **b** Calculated Density of States (light colors) and normalized transmission spectra (strong colors) at zero voltage, distinguishing between the transmission for spin-up (red) and spin-down (blue), where the up-down reference is the polarization direction of the f electrons in the lanthanide. A sharp spin-down conduction peak near the Fermi level is marked with a dashed line as the main conducting peak at low gate voltages.

Methods

SAM preparation. The metalloprotein-based SAMs are prepared following a similar strategy from the typical growth in solution method used for alkanethiol on gold. Substrates made of thermally evaporated metal on a Si/SiO₂ wafer are immersed during 24 h in a 0.1 mM buffered solution of LBTC in the presence of an excess of Tb^{3+} . This procedure ensures formation of a monolayer with high surface coverage as observed experimentally (Supplementary Information sections S1-S5 including luminescence studies, AFM, MALDI-TOF, XPS, and QCM).

Spin-dependent cyclic voltammograms and Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. LBTC grafted on 5 nm Au overlayers onto a 200 nm Ni (Ni/Au) is used as working electrode, Pt, and Ag/AgCl are used as counter and reference electrodes, respectively. Freshly prepared and deoxygenated 5 mM Fe^{2+}/Fe^{3+} solution in HEPES buffer are used as the redox mediator, and oxidation, reduction currents were monitored under an external magnetic field of 0.35 T applied underneath the TBLBTC modified ferromagnetic Ni. The same set up was used for EIS, but using Gamry 1000E and Gamry 5000E potentiostat/galvanostat controlled by Gamry software. An AC voltage of 10 mV in the frequency range of 10^0 – 10^5 Hz at the OCP was applied. EIS data were analyzed and fitted by means of Gamry Echem Analyst v. 7.07 software.

EGaIn measurements. Spin-dependence by EGaIn method. LBTC grafted on 5 nm Au overlayers onto a 200 nm Ni

(Ni/Au) is used as the bottom electrode and EGaIn drop as the top contact. 6 junctions were measured with 16 I-V curves between -0.2 and 0.2 V for a magnetic field applied of 0.35 T and -0.35 T by a permanent magnet placed under the metallic surface (see details in S6).

Electron transport calculations. First-principles calculations are performed using the SMEAGOL code that interfaces the non-equilibrium Green's function approach (NEGF) to electron transport with density functional theory (DFT). In our simulations, the transport junction is constructed by placing the polypeptide between two Au (111)-oriented surfaces. The exchange-correlation potential is described by the GGA (PBE) functional. The Au-valence electrons are represented over a numerical s-only single- ζ basis set that has been previously demonstrated to offer a good description of the energy region around the Fermi level. In contrast, for the other atoms we use a full-valence double- ζ basis set. Finally, the spin-dependent current flowing through the junction is calculated from Landauer-Büttiker formula.

Supporting Information. UV spectra of LBTC and TBLBTC solution, preparation and characterization of the self-assembled monolayers (SAMs), Atomic force microscopy (AFM) experiments, Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight (MALDI-TOF), X-ray photoemission spectroscopy (XPS), C18S contact angle measurements, Coverage evaluation using quartz crystal microbalance (QCM), Film thickness estimation, Spin-dependent electrochemistry set-up and scan rate dependence measurements, EGaIn measurements

of SAM films on Au, Kelvin probe and ambient pressure photoemission spectroscopy measurements, Charge transport calculations on LnLBTC between two gold electrodes and Determination of the magnetic interaction between the spin polarized current and the spin-orbit momentum of Tb³⁺.

Data availability. The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author on request.

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